

Enabling comprehensive optogenetic studies of mouse hearts by simultaneous opto-electrical panoramic mapping and stimulation

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Description of files accessible under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5501068>

Source data

Excel document containing the raw data used for the statistical analysis presented in the figures of the manuscript and the Supplementary Information. Data for each figure are presented on separate sheets labelled with the respective figure numbers. Data of given figures are organized according to the figure panels concerned.

<Source Data.xls>

Step-by-step protocol

The protocol describes the steps involved in conducting POEMS experiments with mouse hearts.

<Step_by_step_protocol.pdf>

Hardware

(1) 3D print files of heart container

Details regarding fabrication and the type and source of electrode wires and optical fibers are given in the manuscript. 3D print files (.3dm) of the heart container and its attached parts as well as the layout of the PCB are:

<organ_container_left>, <organ_container_right> : heart container
<fluid_reservoir_left>, <fluid_reservoir_right> : fluid receptacle on top of cup
<pcb_holder_left>, <pcb_holder_right> : printed circuit board holder
<mounting_plate> : system mounting base
<heart_model_left>, <heart_model_right> : insertion stop for fibers and wires

<ElectrodInterface.step> : PCB layout files for electrode wire
<ElectrodInterface.PcbDoc> termination board

(2) Optical imaging system:

The optical imaging system consists of a fast CMOS camera coupled to a tandem lens epifluorescence microscope that images the faceplate of the combined fibers onto the

camera. While the camera used (MiCAM Ultima, SciMedia, USA) is in the meantime obsolete, cameras with similar specifications as well as tandem lens epifluorescence microscopes are commercially available.

(3) Electrical mapping system:

Electrical mapping and stimulation require a multichannel recording system. Suitable systems as used, e.g., for stimulation and recording from cell cultures, are commercially available.

Software

Data acquisition:

Acquisition of electrical and optical data was performed using the proprietary software of the two recording systems listed above.

Data analysis:

Following extraction of the relevant data from the files produced by the electrical and optical imaging subsystem, data were analyzed using the following custom-developed software:

<POEMSAalyzer2.zip>

How to compile the software:

1. Extract the folder structure provided within the POEMSAalyzer2.zip file.
2. Open Microsoft Visual Studio 2017 or later and in solution explorer open the "POEMSAalyzer2.sln" solution file which is available in the root of the provided folder.
3. On the menu bar choose "Build" and then choose Build POEMSAalyzer2 in order to compile the software.
4. The executable POEMSAalyzer2.exe file will be available in the "bin" folder after the build process was successful.